

SOCIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF STUDY COURSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401990>

Abstract. Training courses play an important role in improving knowledge and skills in modern society. In this article, a sociological analysis of educational courses is carried out. The social impact of the courses, their role in the society and the motivations of the students are analyzed. These issues are important not only in the field of education, but also in a wider social context.

Key words: Individual, stratification, social integration, migrants, social capital, methodology, social integration, innovations.

СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ КУРСОВ

Аннотация. Обучающие курсы играют важную роль в совершенствовании знаний и навыков в современном обществе. В данной статье проводится социологический анализ образовательных курсов. Анализируется социальное влияние курсов, их роль в обществе и мотивация студентов. Эти вопросы важны не только в сфере образования, но и в более широком социальном контексте.

Ключевые слова: Индивид, стратификация, социальная интеграция, мигранты, социальный капитал, методология, социальная интеграция, инновации.

Study courses of society in development and of individuals himself - himself in development main of the factors one is considered Education of people social - economic situation improvement, new profession - trades learning, social activity increase, new skills take over and work in the market competitive to be big important. [1]

1. Social stratification and inequality: Education courses through a lot people new knowledge and skills occupied, social in stratification up the climb opportunity have will be But this in progress social inequality too to the eye thrown because all layers for one different level opportunities not created For example, economic in terms of strong of families their children more and better quality to courses to attend opportunity have will be This in progress situation financial towards is worn.

2. Social integration: Training courses help to increase communication between different social groups and facilitate their adaptation to society. Language and culture courses are especially important for migrants or newcomers.

Students' motivations. The motivations of the participants in the training courses are different. These motivations are related to their social status, economic status and personal needs. Here are some examples [2]:

1. Professional development: Many students new the work to find or present the work in place the climb for to courses participates. Especially today 's demand has been programming, technical or professional courses market requirements adaptation for important.

2. Personal development: Some students think knowledge expand and new abilities learning for study courses they participate. Such motivation personal development and self understanding with depend.

3. Social networks and links: Courses to the students social in networks activity increase and colleagues with connections expand opportunity will give. And this is his in turn, social of capital to increase take will come.

Courses types and their social influence. Study courses different to species divided into : language courses, professional courses, technical courses, culture and art courses and others hand one get up to himself special social to the effect. [3]

1. Language Courses: Language courses, especially abroad in hand living and working migrants for important this courses of students new to the environment adaptation makes it easier and they are with local of the population mutually communication improves.

2. Professional and technical courses: These courses of students work in the market competitiveness increases. They are new technologies and methodologies with introduces this while economic to development positive effect shows.

3. Culture and art Courses: Such courses of student's aesthetic taste develop and their creative potential increases. With that together, this courses social solidarity strengthens and cultural inheritance to keep help will give.

Study courses social in development importance. Study courses social development in the process one series positive effects shows. They are not only knowledge and skills increase, maybe social networks expansion, social integration strengthening and cultural inheritance also important in storage role plays. [4]

1. Social of capital increase: Study courses through people new connections installs and social networks expands. And this own in turn social of capital to increase take will come. Social capital while own in turn economic and personal to development help will give.

2. Social integration and cooperation: Courses different social groups in the middle cooperation and mutually to understand increases. And this social solidarity strengthens and in society balance provides.

Innovations and technological Development: Professional and technical courses innovations encourages and technological to progress contribution adds Through these courses, students will have the opportunity to master new technologies and introduce innovations in their fields.

Study courses modern education in society and social of development important structural part is considered They create opportunities for social stratification, economic development and personal growth. Various forms of courses and the achievements achieved through them have a wide social impact in society. Therefore, it is important to develop training courses and ensure their availability to all social groups. Education system development of society future progress and of well-being warranty is considered. [5]

Population in the middle conducted small questionnaire as a result according to study courses social in life place about the following we know can:

Age

38 answers

Your role in society

38 answers

Are you familiar with the activities of educational centers in your region?

38 answers

What is the effect of additional courses on education do you think?

38 answers

How do you feel about school students and applicants going to courses?

38 answers

REFERENCES

1. <https://class-descriptions.northwestern.edu/4890/WCAS/SOCIOL/29066>
2. Normamat Mallaev Ramazanovich. (2022). CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL STATUS OF MASS MEDIA. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), 3(11), 70–78.
3. <https://www.nord.no/en/events/research-phd-course/phd-course-sociological-analysis-how-to-use-theory-in-the-analysis-of-empirical-data-sos9004>
4. Mamanovich, R. K. (2021). Components of political culture in political processes. *Academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*, 11(2), 953-959.
5. <https://class-descriptions.northwestern.edu/4920/UC/SOCIOL/20322>
6. <https://www.lunduniversity.lu.se/lubas/i-uoh-lu-SOCN06>